

BIBLIOMETRIC ANALYSIS OF EARNINGS MANAGEMENT AND FRAUD: WHERE ARE WE HEADING?

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Abstract

Earnings management and fraud in business is a rapidly growing area of research covering both academia and business. The aim of this study is to identify current research and emerging trends and to provide a comprehensive structure of the knowledge map of earnings management in line with recent developments in bibliometric analysis. Therefore, this paper provides a comprehensive bibliometric analysis based on performance analysis and scientific mapping of the published literature on earnings management between 1912 and 2024 in 14519 publications on Web of Science and Scopus. By utilizing the visual bibliometric software, VosViewer by applying different bibliometric analyses such as co-citation analysis, co-author analysis, bibliographic coupling, keyword co-occurrence analysis, and chronological analysis, this paper presents the fundamental characteristics of knowledge in its research field while identifying the most influential publications, institutions, source titles, source countries and authors, and the evolution of keywords over these years. The paper concludes with discussions and conclusions on the most popular research topics and the identification of future research directions in earnings management and fraud.

Keywords: earnings management, fraud, bibliometric analysis, co-authorship analysis, bibliographic coupling.

Bibliometrics is a research medium, which uses mathematical and statistical techniques for the study of publications and the information that is contained in them (Diodato & Gellatly, 2013). In other words, bibliometrics deals with the statistical and mathematical analysis of words, citations, number of publications, authors, usage of publications, etc.

Bibliometric analysis is a crucial method in academic research, providing an objective picture of the current state of knowledge in a given field. By examining data from databases such as the Web of Science and Scopus, researchers can assess trends, contributions and research directions in the field of earnings management and financial fraud.

This analysis provides the opportunity to identify authors, institutions and countries with significant contributions to the field as well as keywords. It can also highlight the most cited publications and emerging research trends.

Therefore, bibliometric analysis is an essential tool for planning and guiding research in the field of earnings management and financial fraud. The main objective of bibliometric analysis is to provide an overview of existing studies on earnings management and financial fraud, allowing us to identify the most valuable articles, institutions, sources, countries and authors. Bibliometric analysis can provide a foundation for current studies in the research field, helping to detect emerging trends in future research.

According to some researchers Wang et al. (2021); Wang et al. (2021); Wang et al., (2022) the

comprehensiveness of a broad research field finds its solution in bibliometric analysis, it is the most suitable for revealing keywords and future research directions, and it is the most effective way to present the development and relationships between articles and a particular topic or a journal through the analysis of relevant literature.

Researchers Wang et al. (2021); Wang et al. (2021); Wang et al., (2022) and Xu, et al. (2021), identified that bibliometric analysis is an effective statistical method based on quantitative analysis, which has the potential to provide researchers with a comprehensive overview of a research field. Bibliometric analysis has the advantage of highlighting the current state of research and development trends. Thus a well-grounded bibliometric analysis can lead to future research directions that would further develop the investigated research field (Wang et al., 2022).

Some researchers have also identified the reasons behind the growth of bibliometric analyses: firstly, the constantly changing technology, which accelerates the technical evolution of analysis programs and the development of scientific databases, such as Web of Science, Scopus, etc.; secondly, the awareness of the need to analyze a larger sample of scientific data; thirdly, the identification of the development trends of a research field, which can be identified much easier (Donthu et al., (2021)).

In terms of research topic, the mapping techniques are in turn made up of several indicators:

Co-citation analysis - it helps us to understand

how themes develop in a given research field, this indicator analyzes the cited references of scientific publications in our database and assesses the relationships between cited publications; Co-authors analysis- is one of the most important methods of analysis, because it allows us to analyze research networks and scholars, it can lead to the improvement of the field in which research is carried out, through it we can map with more clarity and rich perspective research, this stage is carried out by intellectual corroboration between research institutions and researchers, having as a basis of analysis the number of jointly authored publications; Bibliographic linkage - indicates us the links between the publications we find in a dataset and their positioning in the network, which indicates us the regular development of the research topics; Keyword Co-appearance Analysis - returns the content analysis of a number of publications in which keywords appear in the abstract, title and content; we start from the premise that these keywords that appear in publications should be closely related to our research topic. This mode of analysis is of particular importance as it returns thematic clusters (Donthu et al., (2021)).

To perform the bibliometric analysis, in this paper we use the software program VOSViewer Van Eck and Waltman (2010), it includes a software that returns three types of scientific maps such as network visualization, overlaid visualization and density visualization. The choice of the software we made according to the most current research in this field Anuar et al. (2022); Caputo et al. (2021); Wang et al. (2021); Wang et al. (2021); Wang et al. (2022); and Ferreira, (2018). The success of the research, in terms of bibliometric analysis, when choosing the software, depends largely on its applicability.

Bibliometric analysis of networks of relevant terms used in research on earnings management and financial fraud

The main objective of this subsection is to identify the current state of knowledge regarding the current research, for the realization of this subsection we have identified the current research from Web of Science and Scopus- platforms in relation to earnings management, financial fraud. Our rational objective is to pursue the realization of bibliometric analysis, of the current studies, by analyzing the indicators. The necessity of this scientific endeavor is necessary and timely, being very useful for researchers and academicians. In order to achieve the objective set

above, we have defined the following secondary objectives:

- Bibliometric analysis of studies focusing on earnings management and fraud using information downloaded from Web of Science and Scopus platforms;
- Surprising the evolution over time of the number of publications related to earnings management and financial fraud;
- Analyzing the evolution over time of the number of citations;
- Identification of institutions, papers, countries that have actively contributed to the development of the research topic;
- Analysis of the top 15 most cited authors;
- Map mapping (co-citation, co-authorship, bibliographic coupling, co-occurrence of keywords).

In terms of research methodology, we follow the steps proposed by Conan and Holder (1979), such as querying the data, downloading the data, processing the data, generating the networks, analyzing and mapping the maps.

Methodology of bibliometric analysis

In order to provide a comprehensive knowledge review on earnings management, fraud, we perform a bibliometric analysis (Alshater et al.(2021); Anuar et al. (2022); Dabic, et al. (2020)) in line with current trends. Database searches were performed according to the PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses) protocol, recently revised by Page et al., (2021), from which we extracted the data we used in the bibliometric analysis. Data were extracted from Web of Science and Scopus databases. The guidelines also provide a diagram that we also use in this subsection (Figure 1). Authors such as, Streimikis and Saraji (2022), have identified several advantages of the PRISMA protocol, such as detailed and rigorous vetting of research to help researchers make bibliometric analyses as accurate as possible, systematic review reports, and meta-analyses.

According to Caputo et al (2021) and Ravisankar et al (2011), WOS and Scopus databases present the most qualitative publications being a reliable source of highly ranked journals. Database selection started on September 1, 2022 and ended on May 17, 2024.

The keywords by which the selection was made must be in the abstract, title or content of the articles.

Fig. 1. Research methodology in bibliometric analysis, according to the PRISMA Guide

The first search returned, for the three keywords, a total of 59,996 publications for the period 1912-2023, followed by refining the results by applying the following filters: only open access articles, in English, in the field of finance, financial management and economics. Excluding some of the articles, a total of 33,356 articles were left for analysis, and in the second stage we further refined the selection to confirm the accuracy of the research. The refinement was a

subjective one, only papers strictly related to economics were included in the sample, leaving 14,519 articles. In Tables 1 and 2 we detail the search process underlying the bibliometric analysis. Following the application of the search criteria, both automatic and manual, the final sample of articles was exported in plain text format, and the value articles were exported in (CSV) format, as required for processing in the software used.

Table 1

Description of WOS search procedures

Category	Refining criteria	Number of items remaining after refining
Search string used	Topic: (financial fraud) OR TOPIC: (earnings management)	21.843
Access	Including both Open Access and others	21.843
Period (years)	We included articles up to 2022, for 2024 there were few	(9)
Field of publication	The search was limited to the following WOS categories: Business Finance (7335), Economics (3045), Management (2706), Business (2297), Business (2297), Ethics (299), Behavioral Sciences (26)Public Administration(375). WOS categories such as engineering, computer, construction, biology, chemistry, medical and others were excluded.	(6834)
Type of document	The search was limited to document-type articles (10,560) and reviews (545). Therefore documents such as editorial materials, paper, book, book review and meeting abstract were excluded.	(4430)
Document language	All articles published in languages other than English were excluded.	(201)
Manual refinement (subjective)	Based on manual refinement, irrelevant ones were also excluded	(800)
Final number of articles included in the bibliometric analysis		9.569

Table 2

Description of Scopus search procedures

Category	Refining criteria	Number of items remaining after refining
Search string used	Topic: (financial fraud) OR TOPIC: (earnings management)	38.156
Access	Including both Open Access and others	38.156
Period (years)	We included articles up to 2022, for 2024 there were few	(50)
Field of publication	The search was limited to the following Scopus categories: Business, Management and Accounting (5549), Economics, Econometrics and Finance (4086). SCOPUS categories such as engineering, computer, construction, biology, chemistry, medical and others were excluded.	(28.521)
Type of document	The search was limited to document-type articles (5,167) and reviews (507). Therefore, documents such as editorial materials, paper, book, book review and meeting abstract were excluded.	(3.961)
Document language	All articles published in languages other than English were excluded.	(146)
Manual refinement (subjective)	Based on manual refinement, irrelevant ones were also excluded	(528)
Final number of articles included in the bibliometric analysis		4.950

Results

Following the methodology described above, in this section we present the results of the bibliometric analysis. The results are presented according to the type of bibliometric analysis applied, such as articles, authors, journals and identification of research themes in the field. The aim of this chapter is to present a comprehensive overview of past, current and emerging trends in financial fraud research.

Based on 14,519 articles on financial fraud, financial accounting, economics and accounting disciplines published in 489 journals, as shown in Tables 1,2, this study is based on 14,519 articles on financial fraud, financial accounting, economics and accounting disciplines published in 489 journals. Further, by presenting several bibliometric indicators, this performance analysis provides an overview of the development and distribution of financial fraud from the following statistical perspectives: number of publications related to financial fraud, number of citations, most active institutions contributing to publications related to fraud and creative accounting,

most active sources for publications related to our topic, most active countries contributing to publications related to financial fraud and highly cited publications in this field.

One can observe an evolution over time of publications related to financial fraud in our database consisting of 14,519 publications from 1912 to 2024, and the evolution of the number of publications over time is shown in Figure 2. Despite the period in which these articles were published, we can observe an increased interest in this research area in recent years (2018-2022). It can be seen that in most years the trend that the publications follow is an increasing one, the peak was reached in 2022; however, this year was not fully included in the sample. This shows us that this area of research related to financial fraud and creative accounting is an area of interest for researchers. Considering also the context of the COVID-19 pandemic, we can say that this pandemic has been a real challenge for companies, regardless of the country in which they are based.

Fig. 2 Number of publications over time

Fig. 3 Evolution of the number of citations over time

In terms of the number of citations, a fluctuation can be observed, as shown in Figure 3. The significant increase in the number of citations received by publications related to financial fraud, especially in the last four years, demonstrates the growing popularity and influence of this topic. Furthermore, it can be seen that the highest number of citations so far was recorded in 2021 (43,464 citations). The highest number of citations (402) was recorded in 2021 for the study conducted by (Dechow et al., 1995).

Table 3 shows the top 15 institutions that have contributed publications to this research area. To get a comprehensive picture of these institutions and their relevance in this field, significant information in terms of number of citations, average number of citations and H-index is provided in Table 3. Web of Science, defines H-index as the result of authors' productivity based on their publications and number of citations. The H-index (or H-index) is a measure used to assess a researcher's

productivity and academic impact. It is defined as the highest h for which the author has h papers that each have at least h citations. In other words, a researcher has an H-index of h if he/she has at least h papers that each have at least h citations.

Thus, the H-index reflects both the quantity and the impact of a researcher's work in the academic community. The higher the H-index, the more influential the researcher is considered to be in his/her field of research. It is important to note that the H-index may vary depending on the database used and the time period considered for the analysis. Analyzing Table 3, we can observe an interesting phenomenon with respect to the Texas A M University System and the University Of North Carolina, which record the same number of publications, but the H-index differs, this suggests that the University of California has 39 publications cited at least 39 times.

Table 3

The 15 most active institutions contributed to publications related to financial fraud

Current number	Affiliations	Number of articles	Country	Number of citations	H-index	Average citations per article
1	State University System Of Florida	320	United Kingdom	7.592	52	28.98
2	University Of Texas System	297	United Kingdom	10.302	53	40.77
3	University System Of Georgia	236	United Kingdom	9.845	53	51.31
4	Pennsylvania Commonwealth System Of Higher Education Pcshe	194	United Kingdom	8.054	54	51.36
5	University System Of Ohio	182	United Kingdom	4.011	36	23.94
6	University Of California System	145	United Kingdom	8.545	47	68.21
7	Texas A M University System	136	United Kingdom	6.706	35	56.29
8	University Of North Carolina	136	United Kingdom	8.885	39	78.65
9	California State University System	131	United Kingdom	2.749	24	21.98
10	University Of Illinois System	126	United Kingdom	5.670	38	49.83
11	State University Of New York Suny System	120	United Kingdom	1.966	24	17.31
12	University Of Texas Austin	119	United Kingdom	5.345	38	50.36
13	City University Of Hong Kong	114	China	4.225	36	43.78
14	Hong Kong Polytechnic University	111	China	4.394	32	49.83
15	University Of Houston	110	United Kingdom	3.033	28	30.48

Note: H-index indicates the number of papers (n) published by an institution with at least (n) citations.

Table 4 lists the top 15 contributing countries in this field of research by number of articles. Following the same procedure as in the previous section to provide a comprehensive picture of the role and relevance of these countries in this field. The most influential countries contributing to the development and global

dissemination of publications in the field of financial fraud are the United States of America (4616 articles cited 76.99 times), China (1385 articles cited 20.244 times), Canada (600 articles cited 11.997 times) and with the fewest articles Singapore 114 articles cited 4.131 times.

Table 4

Top 15 countries contributing to financial fraud publications

Current number	Country	Number of articles	Number of articles	Average Reads Per Article
1	United Kingdom	4616	48.836	76.999
2	Peoples R China	1385	14.653	20.244
3	Australia	687	7.268	9.681
4	Canada	600	6.348	11.997
5	England	436	4.613	10.354
6	Taiwan	398	4.211	4.247
7	South Korea	314	3.322	6.813
8	Germany	239	2.529	3.518
9	India	227	2.402	1.113
10	Spain	224	2.370	5.263
11	France	221	2.338	4.747
12	Italy	204	2.158	3.580
13	Malaysia	173	1.830	1.890
14	New Zealand	163	1.725	2.496
15	Singapore	144	1.523	4.131

Bibliometric maps

The main goal of the bibliometric maps analysis is to map the intellectual structure of the selected research domain Donthu et al. (2021), Caputo et al. (2021), by using some scientific mapping techniques (such as co-citation, co-appearance, bibliographic linkage, co-authorship) combined with bibliometric innovation techniques (such as networks and clustering visualization).

Co-citation bibliometrics

As mentioned above, the co-citation analysis evaluates the references cited by the scientific publications included in the analysis sample and analyzes the relationships between the cited publications. We use this type of analysis for a better understanding of the topic in a particular research area. According to, Ferreira (2018), co-citation analysis allows us to identify publications that are co-cited by other articles, which means that these cited publications are somehow significant and related to the research theme.

Our sample consists of 14,519 articles, 225,104 cited references were identified and we considered a minimum threshold of 20 citations of a cited reference, which contained 3866 cited references that met the threshold. To stimulate the understanding of the article

co-citation analysis, Figure 2 illustrates the network diagram, allowing visualization of the co-citation network of financial fraud researchers. According to Figure 2, there are seven major clusters of cited references, where the largest cluster (red) has 244 cited references, the second cluster (green) has 219 cited references, the third cluster (blue) has 199 cited references, the fourth cluster (yellow) has 149 cited references, the fifth cluster (purple) has 102 cited references, the sixth cluster (light blue) has 45 cited references, and the last cluster (orange) has 42 cited references.

Co-author bibliometrics

Co-author bibliometrics examines the intellectual collaboration between researchers and research institutions based on the number of publications jointly produced. This type of analysis is widely used to understand and assess patterns of scientific collaboration in specific research fields. For our sample of 14,519 articles, a total of 17,327 authors were identified and a minimum threshold of five publications per author was considered; the resulting set comprised 701 authors meeting the threshold. In Figure 8, an overview of the co-authors exposed as a result of the processing is presented.

Fig. 4 Co-cities map

Fig. 5 Co-authors' analysis

Bibliometrics of keyword co-occurrence

The main purpose of keyword co-occurrence analysis is to provide a form of content analysis that allows the identification of connections between keywords in a selected sample of publications. According to Fakhar-Manesh et al. (2021), the significance of this analysis lies in the opportunity to identify thematic areas grouped into thematic clusters. To perform this keyword analysis, in this study, we used another tool namely the Web of Science Keyword Plus Tool. While author's keywords are terms set by authors as representative of the content of their papers, Keywords Plus, provided by WOS, are generated using an automated computer algorithm with words and phrases that commonly appear together in the titles of an article's references (Zhang et al., 1999) claimed that using both Keyword Plus terms and author's keywords, taking into account the minimum threshold for keyword occurrence, 20 keywords were identified out of a total of 2512 keywords.

Therefore, the five most frequently occurring

keywords were earnings management (4525 occurrences), earnings quality (1500 occurrences), accruals (909 occurrences), fraud (338 occurrences) and creative accounting (112 occurrences). To promote understanding of keyword co-occurrence, Figure 6 shows the visualization of the cluster density of high-frequency keywords, which is an enriched visualization because the keyword density is shown separately for each keyword cluster. Another useful chart is the stacked visualization, which allows to identify the temporal distribution of keywords in each cluster (Figure 7).

In the overlay view, keywords are colored according to a score that is calculated based on the average year of occurrence of a keyword. Thus, the colors range from blue (oldest year) to green to yellow (most recent years). Another diagram is presented in figure 8, in this figure we can observe the links between the words grouped in clusters according to the size of the bulleted and the color intensity, thus we can observe the links between words.

Fig. 6 Keyword Co-occurrence density map using cluster density

Fig. 7 Keyword overlap map

Fig. 8 Keyword co-occurrence map in network visualization

Conclusion

Through bibliometric analysis it was possible to quantify the current state of knowledge in our field of research in relation to earnings management and financial fraud. In this chapter a bibliometric analysis was performed using a set of scientific materials downloaded from Web of Science and Scopus platforms.

The main objective of the bibliometric analysis was to provide an overview of existing studies on earnings management and financial fraud, which allowed us to identify the most valuable articles, institutions, sources, countries and authors. The bibliometric analysis can provide a basis for current studies in the research field to help detect emerging trends in future research.

Studying the relevant scholarly articles on bibliometric analysis in the field of accounting and finance using Web of Science and Scopus platforms, the conclusion we have drawn from the research is that such analysis is mainly focused on the evolution of scientific publications, topics, authors, journals, countries and institutions.

The conclusions drawn from the bibliometric analysis are that in recent years there has been a significant increase in the number of scholarly articles dealing with earnings management and even fraud.

References

1. Alshater, Muneer M., Osama F. Atayah, and Ashraf Khan. "What do we know about business and economics research during COVID-19: a bibliometric review." *Economic Research-Ekonomska Istraživanja* 35.1 (2022): 1884-1912. doi:https://doi.org/10.1080/1331677X.2021.1927786
2. Anuar, Azyyati, et al. "Bibliometric analysis

of immigration and environmental degradation: evidence from past decades." *Environmental Science and Pollution Research* (2022): 1-13. doi:https://doi.org/10.1007/s11356-021-16470-1

3. Caputo, Andrea, et al. "Digitalization and business models: Where are we going? A science map of the field." *Journal of business research* 123 (2021): 489-501. doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2020.09.053

4. Conan, J. O. E. L., and M. I. C. H. E. L. Holder. "Variables explicatives de performances et contrôle de gestion dans les PMI." *Universite Paris Dauphine* (1979).

5. Dabić, Marina, et al. "Pathways of SME internationalization: A bibliometric and systematic review." *Small Business Economics* 55 (2020): 705-725. doi:https://doi.org/10.1007/s11187-019-00181-6

6. Diodato, Virgil P., and Peter Gellatly. *Dictionary of bibliometrics*. Routledge, 2013.

7. Donthu, Naveen, et al. "How to conduct a bibliometric analysis: An overview and guidelines." *Journal of business research* 133 (2021): 285-296. doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2021.04.070

8. Ferreira, Fernando AF. "Mapping the field of arts-based management: Bibliographic coupling and co-citation analyses." *Journal of Business Research* 85 (2018): 348-357. doi:https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2017.03.026

9. Page, Matthew J., et al. "The PRISMA 2020 statement: an updated guideline for reporting systematic reviews." *bmj* 372 (2021). doi:https://doi.org/10.1136/bmj.n71

10. Ravisankar, Pediredla, et al. "Detection of financial statement fraud and feature selection using data mining techniques." *Decision support systems* 50.2 (2011): 491-500.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.dss.2010.11.006>

11. Streimikis, Justas, and Mahyar Kamali Saraji. "Green productivity and undesirable outputs in agriculture: A systematic review of DEA approach and policy recommendations." *Economic research-Ekonomska istraživanja* 35.1 (2022): 819-853. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1080/1331677X.2021.1942947>

12. Wang, Xinxin, et al. "A look at the focus shift in innovation literature due to Covid-19 pandemic." *Journal of Business Research* 145 (2022): 1-20. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2022.02.067>

13. Wang, Xinxin, et al. "Service networks for sustainable business: A dynamic evolution analysis

over half a century." *Journal of Business Research* 136 (2021): 543-557.

doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2021.07.062>

14. Wang, Xinxin, et al. "A comprehensive bibliometric analysis of uncertain group decision making from 1980 to 2019." *Information Sciences* 547 (2021): 328-353. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ins.2020.08.036>

15. Xu, Zeshui, et al. "A comprehensive bibliometric analysis of entrepreneurship and crisis literature published from 1984 to 2020." *Journal of business research* 135 (2021): 304-318. doi:<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jbusres.2021.06.051>